

Qualitative Study on Metaphoric Expressions: A Review of Aliyu Kamal's Silence and a Smile and its Impact on Social Language

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Abstract

This paper is design to explore the metaphorical expressions used in Aliyu Kamal's Silence and A Smile and its impact on social language. The study considered the complexity of metaphors can lead to misinterpretations or a lack of understanding in various social contexts, which may hinder effective interaction. This ambiguity can affect relationships, cultural exchanges, and the overall conveyance of meaning in social discourse, highlighting the need for greater awareness and analysis of metaphorical language in different settings. The objective of this study is to explore the Metaphoric Expression of Kamal's Silence and a Smiles and its impact on social language. The paper employs qualitative design approach. The approach is library based which collect and analysis data from primary text. The paper reveals that metaphoric expressions used in Kamal's Silence and a Smile are integral to social language, shaping how we think, communicate, and connect with others. They can enhance clarity and foster cultural understanding, but they also pose challenges in cross-cultural communication. Recognizing the power of metaphors can enrich our interactions and deepen our comprehension of social dynamics.

Keywords: Metaphoric expressions, Smiles, Silence

Introduction

Metaphoric expression is a linguistic device where one concept is used to understand another, often by drawing comparisons that highlight similarities between different domains. This approach is fundamental to how we communicate and perceive the world, significantly affecting social language. Metaphors frame abstract ideas in a more concrete term, making complex concepts easier to understand. For instance, describing time as 'money' (spending time) emphasizes its value and scarcity. Metaphors shape our thinking by influencing how we categorize and interpret experiences (Lakoff, 1992).

Moreover, Lakoff (1992) characterizes metaphor as a distinctive and poetic linguistic expression where words deviate from their standard meanings. The conceptual metaphor theory, initially introduced by Lakoff and Johnson (1980), significantly shapes our understanding of the intricate relationship between human thought and language metaphors, serving as communicative tools, aid in articulating complex thoughts by connecting them to shared experiences. The field has witnessed diverse approaches, as evident in the varied terminology used, including hedges (Glucksberg and Keysar, 1993), metaphorical markers (Goatly, 1997), tuning devices (Cameron and Deignan, 2003), meta-communicative markers (Pramling, 2006), and flagging (Steen, 2007). This diversity emphasizes the significance of metaphorical expression as a crucial area of study.

Drawing on the understanding that metaphorical expression in novels aligns more with local pragmatic strategies than the type of metaphor used, the study employs a contrastive analysis of metaphorical expression across the novel's chapters. The introduction of a genre perspective, inspired by the concept of metaphor expectedness in discourse (Cameron and Deignan, 2003), underscores the influence of communication context and messages within the novel. As metaphors play distinct pragmatic roles in different genres (Skorczynska and Deignan, 2006), the necessity for metaphorical expression may vary, with less expected metaphors potentially requiring anticipation for comprehension.

On the impact on social language, Metaphors can clarify complex social issues, making them relatable. For example, referring to social movements as "waves" can convey a sense of momentum and change. Cultural reflection are equally captured in metaphoric expressions often reflect cultural values and societal norms. Different cultures may utilize distinct metaphors that reveal their worldview, influencing interpersonal communication. Metaphors are powerful tools in persuasion. Politicians and leaders often use them to frame issues in a way that aligns with their agenda, affecting public opinion. Similarly, metaphoric expressions portray social identity and connection. Language users shared metaphors that foster a sense of belonging and identity within groups. They create a common language that strengthens social bonds. While metaphors enhance understanding, they can also lead to misinterpretation if the audience is unfamiliar with the cultural or contextual background of the metaphor.

Therefore, metaphoric expressions used in Kamal's Silence and a Smile are integral to social language, shaping how we think, communicate, and connect with others. They can enhance clarity and foster cultural understanding, but they also pose

challenges in cross-cultural communication. Recognizing the power of metaphors can enrich our interactions and deepen our comprehension of social dynamics.

The problem of this study is to address the challenges in interpreting metaphoric expressions within Aliyu Kamal's Silence and a Smile, particularly regarding how these nuances affect social communication. The complexity of metaphors can lead to misinterpretations or a lack of understanding in various social contexts, which may hinder effective interaction. This ambiguity can affect relationships, cultural exchanges, and the overall conveyance of meaning in social discourse, highlighting the need for greater awareness and analysis of metaphorical language in different settings.

The main objective of this study is to explore the Metaphoric Expression of Kamal's Silence And a Smiles and its impact on social language. The objectives of the study are:

1. To explore how cultural Metaphoric Expressions are expressed in Kamal's Silence And a Smiles.
2. To classify the metaphoric expressions base on their usage.
3. To analyze the impacts of metaphoric expressions on social language and communication

Lakoff and Johnson (1980) explained the notion of metaphor as a conceptual trend that is linked to people's thoughts and behaviors. They further comprehended that metaphor is persistent in everyday life, not just in language but in human thought and action, and our everyday conceptual structure, in expressions of which we reflect and act is a metaphorical system in nature (Lakoff and Johnson 1980). Moreover, Lakoff (1993) asserts that conceptual metaphor is defined as a discrete domain mapping in the conceptual organization, and the realization of such a discrete domain mapping is through metaphorical expressions. The concept of metaphor involves as a mapping of a conceptual domain, the source, onto another domain, the target (Barcelona 2002). He further asserts that the source domain and the target domain are both in different taxonomic domains and not associated by a pragmatic meaning, or they are in different functional domains. In simple explanations, Kovecses (2002) asserts that metaphor can be elaboration from Conceptual Domain (A) to Conceptual Domain (B), which is what is called a conceptual metaphor. Gibbs (2006) puts that metaphor is a sort of cerebral mapping that has an outcome on human being's thinking and mind.

Turner and Fauconnier (1995) pointed out two-domain model, which they argued to be inadequate in metaphoric consideration. They argued that it is conceptual projection, which explicate in conceptual integration and formal expression involves a vast organization of knowledge, such as our knowledge of a journey, dreaming or education. According to Turner and Fauconnier, the two-domain model is highly useful and effective for cognitive studies conceptual metaphors.

Gwarzo (2015) argues on the metaphorical and metonymical expressions of two words namely Hannu 'Hand' and Kai 'Head' in Hausa language. He investigates the conceptualizations of body part terms in Hausa language. The study also examines how the idealized cognitive models (icms) are operating for the creations of the words (Hannu 'hand' and Kai 'head') as metaphors and metonymies. The study critically analyses data and proved the conceptualized metaphor of the terms. The metaphor 'head' stands for cooperation, length, and agreement.

Eniayo and Olubunmi (2016) posit that conceptual metaphor is the expression of a concept in terms of another. Every aspect of language is structurally organize grammaticality to achieve part of figurative language. They focused on the syntactic representation of structural patterns in the conceptual metaphors found in two Nollywood movies: *Aya wa ni* (Yoruba) and *He Goat* (an English movie). The meaning mechanism involved in the interpretation of metaphorical structures. Since the study is based on structural analysis of metaphorical expressions, Chomsky's (1993) minimalist program is used as the main analytical framework.

Theado (2013) argues that metaphoric analysis can be used to gain insight on the conceptualizations of literacy informing English Language Arts educators' the understanding of the meaning and goals of literacy education by a case study. He draws on the theoretical perspective of cognitive linguists. Kovecses (2002) asserts that metaphors is viewed as indicative of an individual's deeply held conceptualizations about a given topic, and language is seen as a means of organizing both our perceptions of and active participation in situations and events.

Methodology

The research design for this study is a qualitative research design. Qualitative research design is concern with capturing the richness and depth of human experiences, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviour. The design typically involves gathering data through methods such as interviews, observations, focus group and analysis of document or artifact (Sambo, 2000). This study attempts to explore the cognitive contents of metaphoric expressions in Kamal's Silence and a Smile and its impact on social language. For collecting data for this study, the research employs both primary and secondary sources. The secondary sources

include the primary text Aliyu Kamal's Silence and a Smile. While at another hand, the study will employ conceptual metaphor theory in the analysis and discussion.

Results

The result of this study will present samples of conceptual metaphor identified in Kamal's Silence and a Smile. The metaphor would be classified into source and target domain, followed by a subsequent discussion of its influence on social language.

Metaphor: Vehicles, with ramshackle structure are plying our roads thus harming or endangering our health (Silence and a Smile: 25)

Source Domain: Vehicles (specifically, poorly maintained vehicles)

Target Domain: Public health and safety

The source domain portrays vehicles representing physical entity that is seen as a cause of harm. Their poor condition signifies negligence or danger. While the Target domain shows how these vehicles, suggesting a broader concern about societal well-being, affect the health and safety of the public. This metaphor highlights the relationship between the state of infrastructure (the vehicles) and its consequences on human health, illustrating a systemic issue within the context described. Similarly, in another conceptual metaphor is identified in the primary text:

Metaphor: What are you going to do with this boy? (Silence and a Smile: 7)

Source Domain: This boy (the child or individual being discussed)

Target Domain: Responsibility and authority in relationships (parenting, marriage)

This metaphor encapsulates a moment of tension and responsibility, reflecting deeper social themes of authority, communication, and relational dynamic. The metaphor expresses **power dynamics**. The phrase implies a discussion about authority and responsibility within family or social relationships. It suggests that one person is being questioned about his role in managing a situation involving a child, which reflects expectations of adult responsibilities. **The metaphor in that situation express evident of conflict and miscommunication.** The dialogue highlights misunderstandings and the tension that can arise in relationships. The person's anger and the respond confusion illustrate how communication can break down, often leading to conflict. Moreover, in the expression of another character Alhaji Malle, the conceptual metaphor can be identified as follows: **Metaphor:** I will gladly marry her off to Ashiru, but I will give her away without a single stick of furniture, without a single grain of salt or sugar (Silence and a Smile: 162).

Source Domain: The act of giving away (marriage, particularly in a traditional context)

Target Domain: The perceived value and resources associated with marriage (economic and social stability).

The conceptual metaphor in this expression highlights the complex interplay of cultural expectations, economic considerations, and gender roles in the context of marriage, offering a lens through which to examine societal values and individual agency. The metaphor reflects traditional practices around marriage, particularly the concept of "giving away" a bride. This practice often carries significant cultural weight, illustrating the role of families in marriage arrangements and the expectations surrounding them.

The metaphor also portrays economic factors as he mention of "without a single stick of furniture" and "without a single grain of salt or sugar" underscores the economic considerations involved in marriage. It highlights concerns about the bride's future stability and well-being, suggesting that she is being sent into a new life without the necessary support or resources. **Similarly**, the language used expresses a sense of resignation or bitterness. By stating that he will give her away without essential items, there is an implication of disregard for her well-being, raising questions about the value placed on her future and happiness.

The metaphors identified in Silence and a Smile significantly impact social language by shaping how individuals perceive and communicate complex social realities. They provide a framework for understanding relationships, responsibilities, and cultural norms. The use of metaphor facilitates deeper insights into societal issues, allowing for nuanced discussions about power dynamics, emotional states, and community support. Moreover, metaphors serve as tools for bridging gaps in communication, particularly in contexts where direct expression may be constrained. They enable individuals to articulate feelings and conflicts indirectly, fostering understanding and empathy in social interactions. By encapsulating complex ideas within relatable imagery, metaphors enrich discourse, encourage reflection, and promote dialogue on critical societal concerns. Ultimately, they reveal the underlying values and beliefs that inform human connections and the collective experience within a culture

Conclusion

The literature above, reviews works that are relevant to the area of research. It reviews the work of prominent scholars in the field of cognitive linguistics, such as Lakoff, Johnson, Kövecses and others who dedicated their time and contributed to the field of cognitive linguistics and language in general. The chapter has come up with so many reviews that benefit to this study. The theoretical framework employed in some of the studies includes the idealised cognitive model and Black's interaction theory, whereas the current study employs the conceptual metaphor theory developed by Lakoff and Johnson (1980).

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